

Studies on Indigoid Dyes: Part VII. 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene Indigos and 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-indole Indigos

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Twelve thioindigoid dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 6-iodothioindoxyl with various *o*-diketones. 6:6'-Diiodothioindigo has also been prepared. Dyeing and other properties of the dyes have been studied and compared with those of the isomeric 5-iodo and 7-iodo substituted dyes.

The preparation and properties of some 2-thionaphthene, indole, acenaphthylene and aceanthrylene indigos, with iodine at 5¹- and 7¹-, have been reported earlier. The present investigation reports the preparation and properties of isomeric 6-iodo dyes of the above classes and also a comparative study of the absorption and molar extinction coefficients of the 5-, 6-, and 7-iodo dyes.

The hitherto unknown 6-iodothioindoxyl has been obtained from 5-iodo-2-carboxyphenylthioglycolic acid, the preparation of which is not reported in the literature. 6-Iodothioindoxyl has been condensed with isatin and its substituted derivatives, and seven new dyes have thus been prepared, represented by

(M)

- M_1 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-indole indigo
- M_2 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-chloro) indole indigo
- M_3 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo) indole indigo
- M_4 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-iodo) indole indigo
- M_5 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5':7'-dibromo) indole indigo
- M_6 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro) indole indigo.
- M_7 : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-3'-(5':7'-dinitro) indole indigo.

A symmetrical thioindigoid dye 6:6'-diiodothioindigo (M_8) has been prepared with a

- 1. Sinha, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 463; 1962, 39, 161.
- 2. Das, Sinha and Sinha, this *Journal*, 1966, 43, 601.

view to compare its properties with those of the isomeric symmetrical 5:5'-diiodothioindigo¹ and 7:7'-diiodothioindigo³ reported earlier.

Four other dyes have been prepared by the condensation of acenaphthenequinone and its substituted products with 6-iodothioindoxyl. These compounds have the general formula (N) :

N₁ : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-8' -acenaphthylene indigo

N₂ : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro) acenaphthylene indigo

N₃ : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo) acenaphthylene indigo.

N₄ : 2-(6-Iodo) thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro) acenaphthylene indigo

6-Iodothioindoxyl has been condensed with acenanthrenequinone to produce the dye, 2-(6-iodo) thionaphthene-1' -aceanthrylene indigo (N₅), with a view to study the effect of addition of a benzene ring to the acenaphthenequinone component.

Among the 6-iodo dyes, currently reported, isatin dyes are generally red or reddish violet, acenaphthene-quinone dyes are orange red or dark red, the diiodothioindigo is reddish

violet and the acenanthrenequinone dye is reddish brown. The dyes uniformly dissolve in pyridine, aniline and also in concentrated sulphuric acid producing characteristic colouration, the original dyes being reprecipitated from the acid solution on dilution.

TABLE I

Dyes	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton
M ₁	deep violet	violet red
M ₂	deep violet	violet red
M ₃	violet	deep violet red
M ₄	violet	deep violet red
M ₅	deep violet	dark violet red
M ₆	light violet	reddish brown
M ₇	reddish violet	deep chocolate
M ₈	violet	reddish violet
N ₁	green	red
N ₂	green	reddish violet
N ₃	green	reddish violet
N ₄	violet	greenish brown
N ₅	violet	pink

The dyes dissolve in alkaline hydrosulphite at 50°-60° producing yellow or greenish yellow (isatin series), deep yellow (diiodothioindigo), violet or brownish red (acenaphthenequinone series), and light yellow (acenanthrenequinone) coloured vat and the original colour was imparted to cotton when exposed to air. Some other characteristic properties of these dyes are recorded in Table I. The absorption maxima have been determined in pyridine solution in a Hilger and Watts' spectrophotometer and are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Dyes	λ_{max}	Log ϵ
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-B	500 m μ	3.905
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-B	503	3.984
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-B	517.5	3.904
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-chloro)B	500	3.895
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-chloro)B	505	4.030
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-chloro)B	518	3.360
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo)B	500	3.957
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo)B	505	4.058
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo)B	519	3.408
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-iodo)B	498	3.881
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-iodo) B	502	4.039
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-iodo)B	522	4.000
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5':7'-dibromo)B	501	3.879
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5':7'-dibromo)B	506	4.090
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5':7'-dibromo)B	521	3.799
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)B	510	4.010
2-(7-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)B	502.5	4.352
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)B	529	3.600
2-(6-Iodo) T-3'-(5':7'-dinitro)B	512	3.922
2-(5-Iodo) T-3'-(5':7'-dinitro)B	528	3.910

TABLE II (continued)

Dyes	λ_{max}	Log ϵ
6:6'-Diiodothioindigo	543	3.455
7:7'-Diiodothioindigo	550	—
5:5'-Diiodothioindigo	566	3.175
2-(6-Iodo)T-AI	515	4.000
2-(7-Iodo)T-AI	518	4.054
2-(5-Iodo)T-AI	527.5	4.259
2-(6-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	515.5	4.007
2-(7-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	520	4.080
2-(5-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-chloro) AI	528	4.360
2-(6-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-bromo)AI	518	4.066
2-(7-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-bromo)AI	520	4.089
2-(5-Iodo)T-8'-(3'-bromo)AI	528	4.116
2-(6-Iodo)T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)AI	512	3.700
2-(7-Iodo)T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)AI	522	4.035
2-(5-Iodo)T-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)AI	532	4.597
2-(6-Iodo)T-1'-acanthrylene indigo	490	3.884
2-(5-Iodo)T-1'-acanthrylene indigo	513	3.944

T=Thionaphthene, B=Indole indigo

AI=Acenaphthylene indigo

In the isatin series the absorption maxima of 6-iodo dyes fall in the order: 5'; 7'-dinitro > 5'-bromo-7'-nitro > 5':7'-dibromo > 5'-bromo, 5'-chloro, unsubstituted > 5'-iodo. The value of molar extinction coefficients are in the order: 5'-bromo-7'-nitro > 5'-bromo > 5':7'-dinitro > unsubstituted > 5'-chloro > 5'-iodo > 5':7'-dibromo.

The absorption maxima of 6-iodo dyes in the acenaphthenequinone series have the sequence: 3'-bromo > 3'-chloro > unsubstituted > 3':4'-dinitro and the molar extinction coefficients are in the order: 3'-bromo > 3'-chloro > unsubstituted > 3':4'-dinitro.

In the acenanthrenequinone series, the 6-iodo dye absorbs less powerfully than 5-iodo dye⁴. It is interesting to note that the fusion of a benzene ring to acenaphthene part of the dye molecule has caused hypsochromic shift.

A comparison of absorption maxima of 5:5'-diiodo¹, 6:6'-diiodo and 7:7'-diiodothioindigo³ shows that they absorb in the order: 5:5'-diiodo > 7:7'-diiodo > 6:6'-diiodo. For the sake of comparison the absorption maximum of 7:7'-diiodothioindigo³ is now redetermined in pyridine solution and found to be 550 m μ (Dokunikhin and Gerasimanko reported 548 m μ). The absorption maxima and molar extinction coefficients of some of the dyes reported in previous publications are collated in Table II for comparison.

The substitution of an iodine atom in the 5-position of the thionaphthene part of the indole indigo and acenaphthylene indigo and diiodothioindigo dye molecules produces the maximum bathochromic shift. The dyes absorb in the order: 5-iodo > 7-iodo > 6-iodo.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5-Iodo-2-carboxyphenylthioglycollic Acid.—4-Iodoanthranilic acid (9 g.) was dissolved in N. NaOH (50 ml.) and the solution was added with constant stirring to aqueous hydrochloric acid (100 ml., 10%). The reprecipitated compound was diazotised at 0°-3°C with sodium nitrite (2.1 g.) solution in water (21 ml.). The diazo solution was added with stirring to a mixture of potassium xanthate (6 g.), anhydrous sodium carbonate (12 g.), water (90 ml.) and ice (30 g.). Decomposition of the diazonium compound took place with the separation of a reddish brown liquid as it was slowly warmed up to room temperature (34°). The liberated oil was taken up in strong aqueous caustic soda and the solution was heated on a steam-bath for 3 hr. Sodium chloroacetate, prepared by adding sodium carbonate to monochloroacetic acid (6 g.) was added and the mixture was again heated for 45 min. The mixture was subsequently cooled in ice and on acidification with excess of hydrochloric acid afforded 5-iodo-2-carboxyphenylthioglycollic acid as a yellow precipitate. It was purified by recrystallisation from hot water (charcoal) and finally obtained as a yellowish crystal (9 g.), m. p. 219° (shrinks at 206°). (Found: C, 32.23; H, 1.95. C₉H₇O₄IS requires C, 31.95; H, 2.07%).

6-Iodothioindoxyl.—Sodium hydroxide (12 g.) was moistened with a little water (1 ml) and heated till a thick paste was obtained. 5-Iodo-2-carboxyphenylthioglycollic acid (3 g.) was added gradually for 15 min. to the paste, and kept at 170°-180°. The heating was continued for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. after the addition was complete. The melt was cooled, dissolved in water, acidified with hydrochloric acid in presence of crushed ice. The crude product thus obtained, was purified by distilling with superheated steam. The distillate which solidified as pale yellow leaflets (0.6 g.) was recrystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60°-80°) as pointed needles, m.p. 153°-154°. (Found: C, 35.11; H, 1.94. C₈H₅OIS requires C, 34.78; H, 1.81%).

TABLE III

S-6—*Iodothioindoxyl*

Dyes	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
M ₁	Isatin (0.271 g.) + S (0.414 g.) + AcOH (15 ml.)	Long stout needles	0.48 g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₂ NSI	I, 31.38% S, 7.75	I, 31.35% S, 7.9
M ₂	5-Chloroisatin (0.363 g.) + S (0.552 g.) + AcOH (15 ml.)	Clusters of small needles	0.76 g.	> 315°	C ₁₄ H ₇ O ₂ NSCl I	Cl, 8.12 I, 29.12 S, 7.39	Cl, 8.07 I, 28.89 S, 7.28
M ₃	5-Bromoisatin (0.283 g.) + S (0.345 g.) + AcOH (15 ml.)	Clusters of small stout needles	0.472 g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₂ NS Br I	S, 6.45	S, 6.61
M ₄	5-Iodoisatin (0.478 g.) + S (0.483 g.) + AcOH (27 ml.)	Bundles of fine long needles	0.74 g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₂ NSI ₂	I, 48.21 S, 5.93	I, 47.83 S, 6.02
M ₅	5:7-Dibromoisatin (0.534 g.) + S (0.483 g.) + AcOH (15 ml.)	Long stout needles	0.94 g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₅ O ₂ NSBr ₂ I	S, 5.6	S, 5.7

TABLE III (continued)

Dyes	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
M ₆	3-Bromo-7-nitroisatin (0.474 g.) + S (0.483 g.) + AcOH (20 ml.)	Star shaped crystals	0.82g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₄ N ₂ BrIS	39.0 Br+I,	Br+I, 39.13
M ₇	5:7-Dinitroisatin (0.474 g.) + S (0.552 g.) + AcOH (19 ml.)	Granular crystals	0.87g.	> 315°	C ₁₆ H ₆ O ₆ N ₂ SI	I, 25.73 S, 6.34	I, 25.65 S, 6.46

TABLE IV

S=6—Iodothioindoxyl

Dyes	Reactants	Appearance	Yield	M.P.	Formula	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
N ₁	Acenaphthenequinone (0.28 g.) + S (0.4 g.) + AcOH (21 ml.)	Foliated needles	0.53 g.	303°	C ₂₀ H ₈ O ₂ IS	I, 29.10% S, 7.2	I, 28.86% S, 7.27
N ₂	3-Chloroacenaphthene- quinone (0.25 g.) + S (0.32 g.) + AcOH (15 ml.)	Clusters of small needles	0.33 g.	304-305° (shrink- ing at 301°)	C ₂₀ H ₆ O ₂ ClSI	Cl, 7.65 I, 27.0	Cl, 7.48 I, 26.76
N ₃	3-Bromoacenaphthene- quinone (0.361 g.) + S (0.414 g.) + AcOH (20 ml.)	Woolly needles	0.63 g.	309°	C ₂₀ H ₆ O ₂ BrIS	Br+I, 40.02 S, 6.26	Br+I, 39.88 S, 6.16
N ₄	3:4-Dinitroacenaphthene- quinone (0.44 g.) + S (0.45 g.) + AcOH (70 ml.)	Granular crystals	0.48 g.	> 320°	C ₂₀ H ₆ O ₆ N ₂ IS	I, 24.12 S, 5.91	I, 23.96 S, 6.03
N ₅	Acenanthrenequinone (0.228 g.) + S (0.272 g.) + AcOH (30 ml.)	Small needles	0.28 g.	> 320°	C ₂₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ IS	I, 26.15 S, 6.42	I, 25.91 S, 6.53

Dye (M₆): 6:6'-*Diiodothioindigo*.—6-Iodothioindoxyl (0.55 g.) was dissolved in hot caustic soda (40 ml., 2N) and treated slowly with potassium ferricyanide solution (5%) until precipitation of the dye was complete. The mixture was heated on the steam-bath for 1 hour to complete the reaction. A deep violet red dye (0.44 g.) was obtained. The dye on recrystallisation from nitrobenzene separated as stout plates, m.p. > 315°. (Found: I, 46.1; S, 11.73, C₁₆H₆O₄I₂S₂ requires I, 46.35; S, 11.67%).

Preparation of other Thioindigoid Dyes.—Isatin or acenaphthenequinone or acenanthrenequinone was dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid and equimolecular proportion of 6-iodothioindoxyl was added. The resulting solution on treatment with HCl (conc., 2-3 ml.) precipitated the dye. The mixture was boiled for 10 to 15 min., filtered while hot, and the residue washed with a little acetic acid and hot water.

The dyes belonging to the isatin series and the acenanthrylene indigo were recrystallised from nitrobenzene whereas acenaphthenequinone dyes were recrystallised from xylene.

Authors' thanks are due to Mr. Amitava Ghose, Bose Research Institute, Calcutta, for his help with spectrophotometer and to Principal L. M. M. Prasad, and Dr. J. C. Banerji, Head of the Department of Chemistry, B. N. College, Patna for laboratory facilities and encouragement.